

**PECULIARITIES OF TRANSLATING NAMES OF HOUSEHOLD ITEMS
IN STORIES TRANSLATED FROM UZBEK INTO KOREAN.**

Doctoral student at the State Institute of Foreign Languages in Samarkand:

Torakulova Dilrabo.

dilrabortoraqulova@gmail.com

Abstract: The article deals with the problem of translating the names of household objects into Korean, which were found during the analysis of the narratives written by Abdulla Kahhor and Odil Yoqubov, and translated from Uzbek into Korean.

Keywords: translation studies, reality, transcription, national proper noun, translation, translation problem.

Translation is an art that illuminates the history, the present, the literature and the language of a country. Translation occupies a greater place in our lives than our literature. Political, economic, scientific and cultural cooperation between different peoples around the world is becoming stronger and stronger, and these relations are unthinkable without translation. Talking about the importance of translation today is like explaining the importance of the sun. Just as there is no life on earth without the sun, there is no communication between different peoples without translation, and no development without communication¹. Nationality is very important in translation. Words and concepts that refer to that nationality are called realias, that is, words specific to that country. Realias include national foods, clothing, national musical instruments, names of household appliances, nicknames, nicknames, urban and rural features, architecture, geographical names, natural landscapes, names of animals and plants, academic degrees, also words denoting rank, caste and other subdivisions, words and expressions denoting institutions, organizations, religious ceremonies and other ethnographic symbols². This article focuses on the problem of

¹ Ergash Ochilov, Nilufar Xodjayeva. Tarjima nazariyasi. – Toshkent: “Innovatsiya – Ziyο”, 2022, p. 5.

² Ergash Ochilov, Nilufar Xodjayeva. Tarjima nazariyasi. – Toshkent: “Innovatsiya – Ziyο”, 2022, p.109.

translating words related to household utensils into Korean. In analyzing the story " Vido " by Odil Yaqubov, the following points were considered.

Originality: "For a week the gentleman has not eaten. He only takes a sip of yogurt from an earthen pot when his bowels are burning³."

Korean translation: “그는 음식을 제대로 먹지 못한지 거의 일주일에 되어서, 타는 듯 한 위의 통증을 느낄 때마다 게피르 (설탕 넣지 않은 신 우유, 요구르트) 한 잔 정도 마실 뿌니었다⁴. (Кымын imshigil chedero mokji motxanji koi ilchuire tveoso, tanin тыт хан vie to‘ngchingil nikkil temada керігы (soltang nohji anin shin uyu, yogurгыты) хан chang chongdo mashil puniota) ”.

In the above original passage, the word "ceramic jug," one of our national household items, was not translated into Korean by the translator, but was omitted. However, the Korean people also had ceramic jugs called 도자기. They were used as household items. In Korea, the production of ceramic jugs reached the level of an art as early as 800-1000 years ago. There is information that China and Japan also bought from Korea at that time.

If the translator had translated the word도자기 as hell, this Korean word would have made this object appear even more vividly before the reader's eyes.

Originality: Even now, three or four people have been chatting in front of the big window since noon⁵.

Korean translation: “오늘 점심 때 즘 부터 방문 앞뜰의 **평상에** 마을 사람 서너 명이 앉아 있었다⁶. (O‘nil chomshim te chim puto pangmun apdiri pyongsange mail saram sono myongi anja isotta) ”. In the explanatory dictionary of

³ Odil Yoqubov. Vido hikoyalar. – Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston”, 2015, p.87.

⁴ XX asr o‘zbek hikoyalaridan A.Alimbekov. – Toshkent: Adib, 2014, p.59.

⁵ Odil Yoqubov. Vido hikoyalar. – Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston”, 2015, p.86.

⁶ XX asr o‘zbek hikoyalaridan/ A.Alimbekov. – Toshkent: Adib, 2014, p. 58.

the Uzbek language, the word "suri" is defined as follows: 1. Vertical or sloping in the form of a shed for growing vines, cucurbits and similar creeping plants. elevated device. 2. A four-legged wooden platform built for placing things and eating. 3. A large board is a bed⁷. In the Kareese language there is an exact alternative to the word sori, which is 지지대, 지주대. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language there are 3 different definitions of the word "suri", and these words fully correspond to the first-mentioned definition. According to the translator, the word sori is translated with the word 평상, which has the translation supa. Koreans used this product to rest and eat outside the house by placing a seat around the 평상 (pyongsang). We can say that this translation, which was done by the translator, was done successfully. The story " Dahshat " by Abdulla Qahhor was also analyzed.

Originality: Nodirmohbegim stretched his foot from inside the *sandal*, pinched Unsin's calf and gestured with his eyes, "Surprise, he didn't understand, stop, don't talk"⁸.

Korean translation: 노디르모흐베김은 *탁자 밑으로* 말을 뺀어 운슨의 정강이를 치며 “다행히 이해하지 못했으니, 더는 말하지마.”라는 뜻으로 눈짓을 보냈다⁹. In this translation, we will first focus on the word "*sandal*" because things like sandal are not used in Korean everyday life, so it is a bit more difficult to translate such words. The translator translated this word as 탁자 밑 (takcha mit)"under the table". "Sandal is a means of local warming. It has been used in Central Asia and Eastern countries since ancient times. For sandals, a hole is dug at one end of the room and the inside is plastered in a special way. A bed is placed on it and covered with a blanket. It consists of a bed around which blankets are

⁷ O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. O'zbekiston millioy ensiklopediyasi. – Toshkent: Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, p.618.

⁸ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqol", p. 80.

⁹ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqol", p. 90.

placed. Coal or saxavu coal is put inside. In the cold of winter, he puts his feet and hands in sandals to keep warm"¹⁰. To heat the house, in ancient Korea, a special building was built in the basement of the house, a fire was lit, and the house was heated in this way, which was called **운돌방** (undo'lbang). Sandal and **운돌방** (undo'lbang) are similar in function but differ in appearance. In the translator's translation, the word "sandal" was not found at all. If the translator had translated the word "sandal" according to the transcription method, i.e., left it as it is, and left a commentary on the word "sandal" in the link, he could have preserved the nationality and historicity of the text in the translated text and with the Korean reader. This would have helped to create an idea of our national items unique to the Uzbek people. Analysis of the story " Adabiyot muallimi " by Abdulla Qahhor.

Originality: Mukarram came in with a samovar, Hamida jumped up, took the samovar from her sister's hand and put it on the table¹¹.

Korean translation: 그 때 무가르람이 주전자를 들고 들어왔다. 하미다는 어른 이어나 언니의 손에서 주전자를 받아 탁자 위에 놓았다.¹²

A samovar is a "household appliance"¹³ for making tea, with a water tank and a stove. At present, the translation of realities is one of the main problems of translation studies. For this reason, the translation of realities can cause some difficulties for the translator. In translating the word **samovar** mentioned in the above text, the translator translated the word **samovar** with the word **주전자** (Chujancha), which means teapot, and tried to preserve the meaning. Since the Korean people did not have a tea culture, they did not use things like a **samovar**, but filled water into a pot and boiled it on the stove, and the pot was called **가마솥** (gamasot). Another

¹⁰ O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi. – Toshkent: Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, p.438.

¹¹ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlol", p.71.

¹² U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlol", p.75.

¹³ O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi. – Toshkent: Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, p.435.

example is the story " Boshsiz odam " by Abdulla Qahhor, which helps to create the idea of the *samovar*.

Originality: In any case, the child should be weaned. He wraps his love in a blanket and envelops it like a newly created "kigizday"¹⁴.

Korean translation: 무슨 수를 쓰더라도 아이를 지워야 했다. 그래서 메흐르를 이불로 둘둘 말아서 공처럼 굴렸다.¹⁵

"Kigiz" is a thick, thick blanket made of wool¹⁶. It was used mainly by the peoples of Central Asia. In many cases it is made of sheep's wool. The translator translated the word felt with the method of word substitution by a word that has the translation of 공 (kong) - ball. The situation in the text is reflected in the translation. Since the Korean people were not rich in livestock since ancient times, they did not possess felt and similar items. By using the word *koptok* instead of the word felt, the translator was able to convey the original situation to the owners of the translation language to make it understandable to the reader.

To sum up, one of the main tasks of translation studies is nationality and its manifestation in translation is considered the main problem. It is in the nature of things that the words and information in the original text and the translated text do not completely coincide, that is, the worldview and thinking of the speakers of the original text and the translated languages differ from each other. Therefore, concepts that are fully understandable to native speakers may be less understandable to native speakers. A translator must be able to provide a translation that is both appropriate and understandable to the target language.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati. O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi. – Toshkent: Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti.

¹⁴ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqol", p.15.

¹⁵ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqol", p.19.

¹⁶ O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati. O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi. – Toshkent: Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, p.364.

2. U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: “Istiqlol”.
3. Odil Yoqubov. Vido hikoyalar. – Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston”, 2015.
4. XX asr o‘zbek hikoyalaridan/ A.Alimbekov. – Toshkent: Adib, 2014.
5. Ergash Ochilov, Nilufar Xodjayeva. Tarjima nazariyasi. – Toshkent: “Innovatsiya – Ziyo”, 2022.